

Legal Overview Human Genetics and Genomics: Germany

[WP 2 - Human Genetics and Genomics]

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Executive Summary

Goal(s)

The aim of this report is to give an overview of the legal framework, legal developments and the legal scholarship debate regarding human genetics and genomics in Germany.

Approach

We searched in Google and special German legal data bases, e.g. “juris”¹, for relevant laws, guidelines and legal cases. Furthermore, we searched for academic literature and public opinion papers that reflect the public debate on perceptions and trends regarding genetics and genomics practices in Germany.

Main Findings

Our analysis showed that human genetics and genomics are on a first look regulated very strictly in Germany. The most relevant applicable German laws are the *German Embryo Protection Act* (Embryonenschutzgesetz – EschG)², the *German Genetic Engineering Act* (Gendiagnostikgesetz – GenDG)³ and the *German Code of Criminal Procedure* (Strafprozeßordnung – StPO)⁴. Relevant are furthermore the *German stem cell act* (Stammzellgesetz – StZG)⁵, the *basic law* (Grundgesetz – GG)⁶ and various European guidelines which are implemented in national law. Although on a second look, it seems rather unclear if human genetics and genomics are regulated so clear. There is an ongoing debate on how the Embryo Protection Act can or should be interpreted and furthermore there is an ongoing debate on the usefulness of the Genetic Engineering Act, especially regarding the regulation of preimplantation genetic diagnosis.

¹ Juris. Website: <https://www.juris.de/jportal/index.jsp>

² German Embryo Protection Act. Act on the Protection of Embryos (Embryonenschutzgesetz - ESchG) of 13 December 1990, Bundesgesetzblatt 1990 Part I pp. 2746-2748, amended by Article 1 of the Act of 21 November 2011 (Bundesgesetzblatt 2011 Part I p. 2228).

³ German Genetic Engineering Act. Act on the Regulation of Genetic Engineering. Gesetz zur Regelung der Gentechnik. (Gentechnikgesetz - GenTG). Unauthorized translation: <http://web.uni-frankfurt.de/si/gentech/GenTGengl10-95c.pdf>

⁴ Strafprozeßordnung in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 7. April 1987 (BGBl. I S. 1074, 1319), die zuletzt durch Artikel 2 des Gesetzes vom 30. Oktober 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3618) geändert worden ist

⁵ German Stem Cell Act. Act ensuring Protection of Embryos in connection with the importation and use of human embryonic stem cells, Gesetz zur Sicherstellung des Embryonenschutzes im Zusammenhang mit Einfuhr und Verwendung menschlicher embryonaler Stammzellen Stammzellgesetz (StZG- Stem Cell Act), 14 August 2008 at <http://bundesrecht.juris.de/stzg/index.html>

⁶ German Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany in the revised version published in the Federal Law Gazette Part III, classification number 100-1, as last amended by Article 1 of the Act of 23 December 2014 (Federal Law Gazette I p. 2438).

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Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
Task 2.2	This report is part of and, will provide input to deliverable 2.2.

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Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
GT	Genetic testing
DTC	Direct-to-consumer
PGD	Preimplantation genetic diagnosis

Table 2 Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Genetic Test	A genetic test: is an assay performed to obtain genetic information (directly on DNA or even on other molecules (RNA, proteins), which by extension could give us genetic information.
Genetic Testing	Genetic testing is usually offered to individual patients based on specific individual need on a one-on-one basis (diagnostic testing, prenatal testing, etc. https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/uses). An assay (a genetic test) would be conducted after the clinician has decided to prescribe the test to the specific patient in question. Genetic testing is a type of medical test that identifies changes in chromosomes, genes, or proteins. The results of a genetic test can confirm or rule out a suspected genetic condition or help determine a person's chance of developing or passing on a genetic disorder. ⁷ Genetic testing could be accessed through a health care provider as part of clinical medical care, or as a service or product offered directly to consumers. Issues genetic testing raises relate to access rights, protection of integrity, medical oversight when these tests are being offered, as well as genetic counselling, and quality. Other questions that relate to genetic testing emerge in the area of advertising and the use of genetic information. In regard to advertising such issues as, for example, whether genetic testing providers are or are not allowed to advertise their offered genetic tests emerge (contrast with a distinction being made for advertising prescription and non-prescription drugs). ⁸ In regard to genetic information, such issues as who can access one's genetic information, and how this information could be

⁷ US National Library of Medicine, https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/genetic_testing, accessed 10 July 2018.

⁸ Please consult Louiza Kalokairinou, Pascal Borry, Heidi Carmen Howard, Regulating the advertising of genetic tests in Europe: a balancing act, *Journal of Medical Genetics*, Volume 54, Issue 10.

	used for different purposes, for example, life insurance. One of key issues that emerges in this regard is discrimination relating to one's genome.
Genetic Screening	Genetic screening can have a few different meanings that differ based on subtle nuances and contexts, but in general, we contrast genetic screening from genetic testing because screening is offered to an entire group of people (not specific individuals). In particular screening cases, like newborn screening, for example, the screening programme follows public health frameworks (as opposed to genetic testing which is not a public health programme but within a clinical specialty; in countries where public health programmes don't differ so strongly from clinical practice, you may want to ignore this if it confuses you more. Differences between public health programmes and clinical (one patient at a time) programmes could mean differences in how we approach consent and the obligatory nature of any programme). Other than the "group/population" aim of screening programmes, screening programmes can vary hugely in different ways: population/group targeted (population wide? Certain people/mothers at higher risks as a group?) etc.
Gene Editing/Genome Editing	<p>Gene editing is a relatively recent term used for the description of modifying DNA (you may have previously heard in the past recombinant DNA technology or similar terms that all overlap in some fashion); the term gene editing has come along with the advent of particularly powerful and accurate tools like CRISPR-Cas9 (which is a tool that helps to change DNA). Gene editing can also be referred to as genome modification, which is more holistic, if you will as a concept, but addresses the same ideas; it basically includes not only changing individual DNA in one location but also many changes throughout the genome. One can edit genes in somatic cells (which are not inherited) or one could edit genes in gametes or germline cells which are inherited and would pass down, in theory, DNA modifications/edits to future generations.</p> <p>The term human genome germline modification then includes the modification of 1 or many bits of DNA in an inheritable human cell. Many authors also include the replacement of mitochondria from one embryo to another as a type of germline modification, though this can be argued as (not) being very distinct from DNA modification, for the sake of comparison with other studies, we will include it for the purposes of this SIENNA study.</p>

Part I

1. National legal system in context

1.1 An overview of Germany's legal system

Germany is a member of several international organizations and legal orders that are relevant for a discussion of genetics and genomics. Key organizations and legal orders include the United Nations (UN), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), as well as the Council of Europe (CoE), and the European Union (EU). 96 members of the European Parliament are from Germany. When it comes to international law most experts would say that Germany has a monist system of law; that means, international law and domestic law are parts of a united system. Although in the German scholarship debate there is also the view that the provisions of the Basic Law neither confirm nor deny the proposition that Germany has a monist system.⁹ “Whether or not Germany is monist or dualist, it is clear that the *Basic Law* is friendly towards international law.”¹⁰

1.2 Germany and United Nations

Germany, or rather both parts of Germany (Federal Republic of Germany and German Democratic Republic), joined the UN in 1973. Since 1990 re-unified Germany is a member. Germany has contributed to several UN treaties that affect national laws and policies in the area of genetics and genomics.

1.3 Germany and UNESCO

Germany joined UNESCO on 11 July 1951. Although within the framework of UNESCO binding treaties have not been adopted, the soft measures that are of relevance to shaping genetics and genomics regulatory responses and policies are:

- Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights (1997);¹¹
- International Declaration on Human Genetic Data (2003).¹²
- Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005);¹³

1.4 Germany and OECD

Germany became a member of the OECD on 27 September 1961.

“The OECD responses in the area of genetics and genomics include:

- Guidelines for Human Biobanks and Genetic Research Databases;¹⁴
- OECD Guidelines for Quality Assurance in Genetic Testing;¹⁵
- Guidelines for the Licensing of Genetic Inventions;¹⁶

⁹ Cf. Kunig 2001, pp.28 ff.

¹⁰ Lovric 2006.

¹¹ <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genome-and-human-rights/>

¹² <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genetic-data/>

¹³ <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/bioethics-and-human-rights/>

¹⁴ <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/guidelines-for-human-biobanks-and-genetic-research-databases.htm>

¹⁵ <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/oecdguidelinesforqualityassuranceingenetictesting.htm>

¹⁶ <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/guidelinesforthelicensingofgeneticinventions.htm>

- Pharmacogenetics;
- Biomarkers and targeted therapies.¹⁷

1.5 Germany and CoE

- On 13th July 1950 Germany became the 14th member State of the Council of Europe.
- The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR):

In Germany, the ECHR is ranked below the Basic Law at the level of the federal law. Although this is in line with state-law provisions, it is subject to the "lex posterior" principle in comparison with federal regulations of the same kind, so that under certain circumstances it could withdraw from more recent legal regulations. However, since the basic rights guarantee of the ECHR largely corresponds to that of the Basic Law, the Federal Constitutional Court ruled in 1987 that other statutory provisions of the Federal Republic (such as the Code of Criminal Procedure) had to be interpreted in the light of the ECHR. This view is also followed by the upper federal courts. Thus, the ECHR is de facto in German law, not a constitutional, but a superordinate rank.

- The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine (Biomedicine Convention)¹⁸ and its protocols,¹⁹ particularly, Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes (APGT): Germany has neither signed the Biomedicine Convention nor the APGT. There is an ongoing debate in Germany. Critics accuse it of going beyond the normative framework which is established by human rights – not least due to the fact that it permits, under limited circumstances, research on persons unable to consent. Among ethicists and jurists, however, the broad consensus is that this criticism is unfounded.

2. Objectives of the report

In line with guidance issued in SIENNA Task 2.2, this report examines Germany's regulatory framework, legal developments and doctrine regarding genetics and genomics as specified for SIENNA Task 2.2. More specifically, it examines:

- Q 1 How, if at all, human germline gene editing is regulated?
- Q 2 Genetic screening in general
- Q 3 Genetic testing in general
- Q 4 Prenatal testing/screening
- Q 5 Newborn screening
- Q 6 Advertising of genetic testing or screening

¹⁷ <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/biomarkersandtargetedtherapies.htm>

¹⁸ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, CETS 164 (hereinafter "Oviedo Convention").

¹⁹ Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Biomedical Research, CETS No. 195.

3. Approach, materials and method

3.1 Literature overview

The following terms were used as key-words for research:

English	German
human germline gene editing	Eingriffe in die menschliche Keimbahn
genetic screening	Genetische Reihenuntersuchungen
genetic testing	Gentests
prenatal testing/screening	Pränatale Gentests/pränatale Reihenuntersuchungen
new-born screening	Neugeborenen screening/Reihenuntersuchung bei Neugeborenen
advertising of genetic testing or screening	Werbung für Gentests/Gentests kommerziell anbieten
These keyword were used in connection with the following:	
Law	Recht/Gesetz
legal	rechtlich
Guidelines	Regeln
Case law	Rechtsprechung
Legal scholarship debate	Rechtswissenschaftliche Debatte

Table 3: key-words

3.2 Legal developments

Beside Google as main data base for our search, we searched for legal developments at the web-pages of German government institutions and furthermore on pages of professional organisations which might have influence on the government, e.g. the national academy of sciences Leopoldina²⁰ or the German research Foundation (DFG)²¹

3.3 Analysis of legislation

The applicable legislation is presented and analysed in each section.

4. Scope and limitations of the report

It was not difficult to find out how genetics and genomics are regulated by law in Germany at a first look. There is the Embryo Protection Act and the Genetic Engineering Act which regulate all relevant areas. Although, at a second look, everything becomes unclear again: There is a debate in the public, politics and legal scholarship regarding the interpretation of the embryo protection act and furthermore there are lots of critics against the Genetic engineering act. Due to time concerns, within this report we can describe these conflicts only very general.

²⁰ Leopoldina. Webpage: <https://www.leopoldina.org/leopoldina-home/>

²¹ German research Foundation. Web page: <http://www.dfg.de/>

Part II

5. Current legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics

Articles and abstracts of articles were selected and reviewed from German law journals, such as the journal “Medizinrecht” (MedRecht), “Gesundheitsrecht” (GesRe). Furthermore we searched for relevant book publications.

5.1 Current legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing

Germline interventions in humans are prohibited in Germany under the Embryo protection Act. Although this is criticised or rather discussed in the debate.

German Ethics Council (2017)

The German Ethics Council published ad hoc recommendations on “Germline intervention in the human embryo” in 2017.²² The main message of this paper is that the German Bundestag and the Federal Government should work out new guidelines and rules for germline interventions in humans. This should happen in close cooperation with the United Nations.

Gene Technology Report (2018)²³

A well-known German research group is the interdisciplinary research group “Gentechnologiebericht” (gene technology report) which is part of the “Berlin Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften”.²⁴ This group examines current developments in genetic engineering in Germany and aims to provide the necessary groundwork for an unprejudiced and open-minded debate about gene technology in Germany. In 2018 the 4th report on gene technology was published. In this report the group recommends to proof the legal framework regarding gene technology in Germany in general. One specific recommendation is to revise the Embryo Protection Act, with the aim to make more research possible in Germany on the one hand and to close legal gaps on the other hand.²⁵

Leopoldina and German research Foundation (2015)²⁶

Applications of germ line therapy, for which the technology is definitely not mature at the present time, is up for discussion. Apart from the legal situation in Germany, which prohibits germ line interventions, the Leopoldina and its partners support the call for an international moratorium for germ line experiments in humans. The period of the moratorium should be used for further research (which can only partially be conducted in Germany due to legal restrictions) to elucidate the opportunities, the demands and risks of the technology, providing time for a social debate on the ethical, legal and regulatory impacts of germ line therapy. Provided the experimental thresholds are met, the questions arise, how to distinguish between medically based treatment and enhancement of human capabilities and what kind of genome editing in human reproductive applications should be

²² German Ethics Council 2017.

²³ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2018.

²⁴ Website of the „Gentechnologiebericht“ group: <http://www.bbaw.de/en/research/gentechnologiebericht>

²⁵ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2018, p.35.

²⁶ Leopoldina, DFG et al. 2015.

approved. To address these issues the establishment of a model regulatory framework, that could be adopted internationally, seems to be a highly desirable goal.

5.2 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general

Not identified.

5.3 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general

Debate on the German Gene Engineering Act:

In Germany there is an ongoing debate regarding the Gene Engineering Act. Critics assume that past experience has shown that the law complicates the everyday life of the doctors and patients concerned by a variety of regulations. Particularly problematic is the broad scope of the law, as it includes both diagnostic and predictive genetic examinations. The German Medical Association and specialist societies also criticize the cooperation with the Genetic Diagnostics Commission (GEKO), as the guidelines drawn up by the GEKO are in part unworkable.²⁷ A revision of the law was also required in 2010 by the National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina, the German Academy of Science (acatech) and the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences in a joint publication.²⁸ They complain that essential parts of the German Genetic Engineering Act are not up-to-date with the latest technology, that they are hardly feasible in medical practice or have negative effects on the success of recognized preventive examinations (such as neonatal screening). They published 22 recommendations on how to amend the Genetic Diagnostics Act and discuss aspects of genetic testing on healthy people to prevent disease.²⁹

Debate on the use of DNA samples in criminal investigations:

Beside the debate on the *Gene engineering act* there is also a legal debate about the legal framework for genetic testing of suspects in criminal cases. This field is regulated in the *German Code of Criminal Procedure* (Strafprozeßordnung – StPO)³⁰ in the sections 81a-81h StPO. An article, which gives a good overview on this debate, was published by Zöllner and Thörnisch 2017.³¹ They discuss the question if a wider use of DNA samples in criminal cases should be legalized. This question was also discussed by the German federal justice ministry in 2017. In general there are two possibilities to use DNA analysis in criminal investigations. The one is to determine whether a DNA sample from the crime scene or the victim matches with a person – this is also called genetic fingerprinting. The other one is to examine the DNA sample to get more information about what an unknown suspect might look like, e.g. which hair colour, which skin and eye colour and which age. According to the German law, regulated in section 81a-81h StPO, the police may check a sample only for gender. The proposed change of law, would allow the police to analyse DNA examples also for hair, skin and eye colour, and biological age.

5.4 Current legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening

German Ethics Council (2011)³²

Based on previous consideration and discussion, the German Ethics Council already issued an opinion on PGD and two alternative proposals on its legal regulation in March 2011. A majority of 13 members argued in favour of a legalization of PGD through the lawmaker provided there is a high risk such as

²⁷ <https://www.dgti.de/docs/doclink/10836/doc20130215122250.pdf>

²⁸ http://www.leopoldina.org/uploads/tx_leopublication/201011_natEmpf_praedikative-DE.pdf

²⁹ Leopoldina 2010.

³⁰ Strafprozeßordnung in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 7. April 1987 (BGBl. I S. 1074, 1319), die zuletzt durch Artikel 2 des Gesetzes vom 30. Oktober 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3618) geändert worden ist

³¹ Zöllner, Thörnisch 2017.

³² https://www.ethikrat.org/fileadmin/Publikationen/Stellungnahmen/englisch/DER_Stn_PID_EN_Online.pdf

the case “when there is demonstrably a high risk that the parents pass on a chromosomal disorder or otherwise a mutation, which makes an extrauterine survival of the embryo impossible.” Prevented by law should be however the use of PGD to identify gender-related qualities, to detect age-related or late-onset diseases or to select a “saviour sibling”. 11 members of the German Ethics Council held PGD for not justified and hence remained that it should not be legalized. The worries of the genetically prone couples must be taken seriously, so the second assessment. However, taking these worries seriously does not result in justifying PGD, rather it demands a more intensive consulting and support for the families in question

5.5 Current legal academic debates regarding newborn screening

Leopoldina (2010)

„The Gendiagnostikgesetz considers the newborn screening as a genetic survey. Accordingly, since the Gendiagnostikgesetz came into force, the parents must be provided with a genetic consultation before blood is taken. Baby nurses and midwives, who previously took the blood, are no longer allowed to do this on their own responsibility. There are already indications that this is leading to the newborn screening not being carried out for some newborn babies. This can lead to life-long disability, which could have been avoided with early diagnosis and appropriate treatment.“³³

“The Gendiagnostikgesetz should regulate the newborn screening separately and in accordance with the special circumstances. The person, who takes the blood sample as part of the newborn screening, e.g. the baby nurse or midwife, should be allowed to explain the aim of the examination to the parents. The examination should then be dependent on whether the parents provide written confirmation of their consent. If a normal result is provided, the parents would not need to be contacted again. If the findings, on the other hand, were abnormal, the parents should then be provided with extensive information and genetic consultation from the responsible doctor.“³⁴

5.6 Current legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

Leopoldina: „In the case of DTC (Direct to consumer) tests, the same risks exist as for prescription medications, which are prohibited outside the expert groups with good reason. (...) As for prescription medications, a ban on advertising should be anchored in the law for predictive gene tests.“³⁵

5.7 Current legal academic debates regarding another topic not listed above that is nonetheless very important to highlight in your country (OPTIONAL)

Not identified.

³³ Leopoldina 2010.

³⁴ Leopoldina 2010, p. VII.

³⁵ Leopoldina 2010, p. VII.

6. Legal developments in the area of genetics and genomics

6.1 Legal developments regarding human germline gene editing

There is an ongoing debate in Germany about the interpretation of the Embryo Protection Act with regard to germline interventions. The German Embryo Protection Act³⁶ of 1990 prohibits the generation and use of embryos for basic research and for harvesting embryonic stem cells. The act, on the other hand, does not explicitly prohibit gene therapy or gene editing on an embryo that aims to enable its survival or serves its health. Therefore, the German legal situation regarding non-viable embryos is unclear. There is a controversial debate amongst legal experts whether the Embryo Protection Act also prohibits "therapeutic cloning" or whether there is a regulatory gap.

The most relevant publication reflecting this debate is a report published by the *Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities* (especially by the Interdisciplinary Research Group Gene Technology) on "Human Genome Surgery" in 2015.³⁷ In this report the loopholes and inconsistencies in the Embryo Protection Act with regard to germline interventions are described. According to this report the bans made in Section 5 of the German Embryo Protection Act are not very clear or consistent. Various examples are given:

- "For the term 'germ line cell' the Act gives a definition which refers to a direct lineage chain from the individual cells ('one cell line') of the egg cell, sperm cell, fertilised egg cell down to the germ cells of the progeny. There is a loophole in this legal definition as the early embryo does not contain any cells after the first cell division that could be identified as germ cells."³⁸
- "Furthermore, it is unclear whether the germ line alteration would be exempt from punishment when it is undertaken in an embryo which (...) was not viable. Arrested embryos, in which cell division does not take place (any more), are not protected by the Embryo Protection Act. Section 5 ESchG with its ban on germ line alteration does not focus on the embryo and only exempts those germ cells from the blanket ban, which are not used for fertilisation."³⁹
- "Finally, the Act does not contain any statements about whether the term "germ cell" encompasses only naturally formed egg and sperm cells or also artificially engineered egg and sperm cells (e. g. from induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS cells))."⁴⁰
- "What is clearly not covered by the ban on germ line alterations is any alteration to the genetic information of a somatic cell. Nor is the transfer of the cell nucleus of an altered cell to an enucleated egg cell banned by Section 5 ESchG."⁴¹

In this report the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities (BBAW) recommends to judge the new genome surgery methods not in isolation. The context in which they are applied and

³⁶ German Embryo Protection Act

³⁷ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2015.

³⁸ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2015, p. 15.

³⁹ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2015, pp. 15-16

⁴⁰ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2015, p. 16.

⁴¹ Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities 2015, p. 16

the goals they pursue should be considered and any general evaluation of these methods should be avoided.

Another publication has great influence on the legal debate regarding the interpretation of the German embryo protection act: A report on “the opportunities and limits of genome editing” published by the German Research Foundation (DFG), the science academy Leopoldina and other German research institutions.⁴²

The research institutions stress out the great scientific potential of genome editing. They point out that it is ethically and legally acceptable in many areas. „The new techniques should not be automatically equated with sporadic cases of improper use or with applications whose ethical and legal ramifications have not yet been assessed. The DFG and the academies endorse the call for an international moratorium on all forms of human germline engineering that could have an impact on the genome of the offspring. The moratorium should give scientists, politicians and society the opportunity to discuss unresolved questions in a transparent and critical way, to evaluate the benefits and potential risks of the techniques, and to develop recommendations for future regulations. However, the moratorium should not constitute a general restriction on methodological developments and thus limit any promising new genome editing approaches for use in research and application.”⁴³

6.2 Legal developments regarding genetic screening in general

Not identified.

6.3 Legal developments regarding genetic testing in general

As mentioned above in section 5.3 of this report there is an ongoing debate on the use of DNA samples in criminal investigations. According to the relevant German law only *genetic fingerprinting* is possible, that means DNA samples from crime scenes could only be used to identify a person who matches the DNA. Although there is a new law since March 2018, which is only applicable in Bavaria and not in the other parts of Germany, which enforces the police to use DNA samples from crime scenes for more than only genetic fingerprinting, e.g. hair and eye colour and biological age.⁴⁴ A draft of this new legislation was published three month before. The new Bavarian guidelines for the Bavarian police were and are strongly criticised.

6.4 Legal developments regarding prenatal testing/screening

Prenatal testing is regulated in Germany since 2011. The law regulating preimplantation genetic diagnosis was added to the embryo protection act as §3a.

6.5 Legal developments regarding newborn screening

Not identified.

⁴² Leopoldina, DFG et al. 2015.

⁴³ Leopoldina, DFG et al. 2015, p. 19.

⁴⁴ Polizeiaufgabengesetz (PAG) in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 14. September 1990 (GVBl. S. 397, BayRS 2012-1-1-I), das zuletzt durch § 1 des Gesetzes vom 18. Mai 2018 (GVBl. S. 301, 434) geändert worden ist.

6.6 Legal developments regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

At the moment advertising of genetic testing or screening without medical purpose is not regulated in Germany. There have been no relevant legal developments in the last years.

Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics

7. Human germline gene editing

7.1 The applicable law in Germany

Genetic modifications of the human germline, germline therapy and the use of modified germ cells for fertilisation are prohibited in Germany under Section 5 of the *Embryo Protection Act* from 1991.⁴⁵

Section 5

Artificial alteration of human germ line cells

- (1) Whosoever artificially alters the genetic information of a human germ line cell shall be punished with up to five years' imprisonment or a fine.
- (2) Likewise anyone shall be punished who uses a human germ cell with artificially altered genetic information for fertilisation.
- (3) Any attempt shall be punishable.
- (4) Subsection 1 shall not apply to
 1. the artificial alteration of the genetic information of a germ cell situated outside the body, if any use of it for fertilisation is ruled out,
 2. the artificial alteration of the genetic information of any other autologous germ line cell that has been removed from a dead embryo or fetus, a human being or a deceased person, if it is ruled out that
 1. a) it will be transferred to an embryo, fetus or human being or
 2. b) a germ cell will originate from it,and likewise
 3. vaccinations, radiation, chemotherapeutic or other treatments which are not intended to alter the genetic information of germ line cells.

Important is that Section 5 (4) 1 implies that research can be conducted with altered germ line cells, provided they are not used for implantation. Although in the end it is prohibited to use these cells, since the German stem cell act⁴⁶ clearly prohibits the generation of embryos for research. The stem cell act was developed to ensure the protection of Embryos in connection with the importation and use of human embryonic stem cells. The act came into force in 2002 and included a 'cut-off date' of 1 January 2002 – imported ES cell lines must have been derived before that date. In 2008, as a result of pressure from scientists, the act was amended, to move the cut-off point to 1 May 2007. In addition

⁴⁵ German Embryo Protection Act.

⁴⁶ German Stem Cell Act.

to these criteria, embryonic stem cell lines can only be used for research if they are vital in developing new medical and scientific knowledge.

7.2 Regulation of basic research

The German Embryo Protection Act contains a number of prohibitions that are of importance to basic research dealing with human germline gene editing. Although the terms “basic research” or “pre-clinical research” are not explicitly defined. Basic research on human germline genome modification is prohibited by Section 5 in connection with section 8 of the Embryo Protection Act.

“Section 8: Definition

(1) For the purposes of this Act, an embryo shall already mean the human egg cell, fertilised and capable of developing, from the time of fusion of the nuclei, and further, each totipotent cell removed from an embryo that is assumed to be able to divide and to develop into an individual under the appropriate conditions.

(2) In the first twenty-four hours after nuclear fusion, the fertilised human egg cell shall be held to be capable of development unless it is established before the expiry of this time period that it will not develop beyond the one-cell stage.

(3) Germ line cells, for the purpose of this Act, shall be all cells that, in one cell-line, lead from the fertilised egg and sperm cells to the resultant human being and, further, the egg cell from the insertion of or penetration by the sperm cell until the completion of fertilisation by fusion of the nuclei.”

7.3 Regulation of pre-clinical research

German law does not define pre-clinical research. Pre-clinical research, in the sense of research performed to gather information needed to go on to conduct clinical trials, often involves research with animals. Therefore, the German Animal Welfare Act⁴⁷ might be relevant. Its main goal is formulated in section 1: “No one may cause an animal pain, suffering or harm without good reason”. An important amendment of the Animal Welfare Act came into force in July 2013. With regard to animal experiments, most of the changes made in this amendment were prompted by Directive 2010/63/EU⁴⁸ issued by the European Parliament in 2010.

In Section V of the German animal welfare act experiments in animals are regulated. According to section V, article 7 (2):

“Experiments may only be carried out on animals if they are indispensable for one of the following purposes:

1. the prevention, diagnosis or treatment of diseases, suffering, bodily defects or other abnormalities or the detection or exertion of influence of physiological conditions or functions in human beings or animals;
2. the detection of environmental hazards;

⁴⁷ German Animal Welfare Act.

⁴⁸ DIRECTIVE 2010/63/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes

3. the testing of substances or products to ensure that they are safe in terms of human or animal health or that they are effective against animal pests;
4. basic research.”⁴⁹

Relevant is furthermore §11b of the Animal welfare Act:

“(1) It shall be prohibited to breed vertebrates or to change them through procedures of biotechnology or genetic engineering if it must be expected that the offspring, the animals altered by biotechnology or genetic engineering or their offspring due to hereditary factors are lacking parts of the body or organs for species-specific use or they are unfit or deformed thereby causing pain, suffering or harm.

(2) It shall be prohibited to breed vertebrates or to change them through procedures of biotechnology or genetic engineering if it must be expected that in the offspring

- a) behavioural abnormalities will occur entailing suffering or increased aggressiveness caused by hereditary factors or
- b) each species-specific contact with conspecifics causing pain or avoidable suffering or pain to them or a conspecific or
- c) their keeping is only possible under conditions causing them pain or avoidable suffering or harm.

(3) The competent authority may order the sterilization of vertebrates if it must be expected that their offspring will show abnormalities or deformations as set out in paragraphs 1 or 2.

(4) The paragraphs 1, 2 and 3 shall not apply to vertebrates changed through breeding or procedures of biotechnology or genetic engineering, which are necessary for scientific purposes.

(5) The Federal Ministry shall be empowered by ordinance, with the consent of the Bundesrat, if required for animal welfare, to specify in detail the hereditary defects, behavioural abnormalities and increased aggressiveness pursuant to paragraphs 1 and 2 prohibiting or restricting, in particular, specific forms of breeding and breed characteristics.”

Although the Animal Welfare Act seems to be applicable with regard to germline gene editing, it is unclear whether gene editing of an animal germline genome, to study possible clinical applications for humans is prohibited or permitted.

8. Genetic screening in general

The German Bundestag passed the law on genetic testing of humans, the Genetic Engineering Act - (GenDG) on 24 April, 2009. It entered into force on 1 February, 2010 (§ 27).

Genetic screening is regulated in §16 GenDG. Genetic screening may only be carried out when the objective is to find out whether the persons affected have genetic characteristics with significance for a disease or health disorders that are, according to science and technology, preventable or treatable. Furthermore, genetic screening may be started only if the Genetic Diagnostic Commission has assessed

⁴⁹ Unauthorised English translation of an earlier version of the German Animal Welfare Act.
<https://www.animallaw.info/statute/germany-cruelty-german-animal-welfare-act>.

it in a written statement. This Genetic Diagnostics Commission (called GEKO) was according to the GenDG established at the Robert Koch Institute. It is composed by 13 experts from the disciplines of medicine and biology, two experts from the disciplines of ethics and law, as well as two representatives of leading patient and consumer advocacy groups. In 2012 the GEKO published guidelines on genetic screening.⁵⁰ In this guidelines, criteria for new target diseases as well as organizational requirements for genetic screenings are regulated. These are based on criteria on genetic screening developed by the WHO by Wilson and Jungner⁵¹ and based on criteria published by Andermann et al.⁵²

9. Genetic testing in general

Genetic testing regulated in the German Gene Engineering Act:

The German Genetic Engineering Act (GenDG) explicitly regulates genetic testing, in order to ensure the state's commitment to respect and to protect human dignity and the right to informational self-determination (§ 1). Besides the use of genetic testing for medical purposes, the Act regulates the use in the field of insurance (§ 18) and in working life (§§ 19-22).⁵³ Not regulated in the GenDG are questions regarding genetic testing in basic research.

The objective of the GenDG is to avoid discrimination on grounds of genetic characteristics. Furthermore, the Act aims to promote quality assurance in the field of genetic testing: According to the law companies or institutions performing genetic testing must be specifically accredited. Genetic testing for medical purposes may only be carried out by a physician ("Arztvorbehalt" § 7). Diagnostic testing can be conducted by a general practitioner. Predictive testing must be performed by a medical specialist. Before conducting genetic testing, informed consent of the person involved has to be obtained (§ 8). Prior to giving consent, the person concerned shall be informed of the nature, significance and consequences of the genetic test to be performed (§ 9). Performing genetic testing on persons unable to give consent shall only be allowed under certain conditions (§ 14). Moreover, the Act contains provisions relating to genetic counselling (§ 10) and to disclosure of the results of genetic tests (§ 11). In the case of predictive genetic testing, the person concerned shall receive genetic counselling from a doctor with specific qualifications before the test is performed and once the results are on hand, unless this person - after having received written information on the contents of the counselling - has waived their right to genetic counselling in writing. After counselling, the person concerned shall be allowed adequate time for consideration before undergoing the test (§ 10 para. 2).

Genetic testing regulated in the German Code of Criminal Procedure:

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https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Kommissionen/GendiagnostikKommission/Richtlinien/RL_Reihenuntersuchung.pdf;jsessionid=F750DC40A74F02CBC234F29D1A782399.2_cid298?__blob=publicationFile

⁵¹ Wilson JMG, Jungner G (1968) Principles and practice for screening for disease. – Geneva:World Health Organisation. Public Health Papers (No. 34).

http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/37650/1/WHO_PHP_34.pdf.

⁵² Andermann A, Blancquaert I, Beauchamp S, Costea I (2011) Guiding policy decisions for genetic screening: developing a systematic and transparent approach. Public Health Genomics 14(1):9– 16

⁵³ Cf. German Reference Centre for Lifesciences, in focus:

Genetic testing is also regulated in the *German Code of Criminal Procedure* (Strafprozeßordnung – StPO)⁵⁴ Relevant are the sections 81 e)- 81h) StPO.

According to section 81a (1) StPO “a physical examination of the accused may be ordered for the purposes of establishing facts which are of importance for the proceedings. For this purpose, the taking of blood samples and other bodily intrusions (...) shall be admissible without the consent of the accused, provided no detriment to his health is to be expected.” Important is that only a judge can give the authority to conduct this examination without consent of the accused (section 81a (2) StPO) and “blood samples or other body cells taken from the accused may be used only for the purposes of the criminal proceedings for which they were taken or in other criminal proceedings pending; they shall be destroyed without delay as soon as they are no longer required for such purposes” (section 81a (3) StPO). Section 81b rules out that fingerprints of the accused may be taken, even against his will.

According section 81c [Examination of Other Persons] “the taking of blood samples from persons other than the accused shall be admissible without such persons’ consent provided no detriment to their health is to be expected and the measure is indispensable for establishing the truth. The examinations and the taking of blood samples may only ever be carried out by a physician.”

In section 81e genetic examinations are regulated:

“(1) Material obtained by measures pursuant to Section 81a subsection (1) may also be subjected to molecular and genetic examinations, insofar as such measures are necessary to establish descent or to ascertain whether traces found originate from the accused or the aggrieved person; in so doing the gender of the person may also be determined by examination. Examinations pursuant to the first sentence shall also be admissible to obtain similar findings on material obtained by measures pursuant to Section 81c. Findings on facts other than those referred to in the first sentence shall not be made; examinations designed to establish such facts shall be inadmissible.

(2) Examinations admissible pursuant to subsection (1) may also be carried out on trace materials which have been found, secured or seized. Subsection (1), third sentence, and Section 81a subsection (3), first part of the sentence, shall apply mutatis mutandis.“

Furthermore section 81f states:

„(1) Without the written consent of the person concerned, examinations pursuant to Section 81e subsection (1) may be ordered only by the court and, in exigent circumstances, by the public prosecution office including the officials assisting it (section 152 of the Courts Constitution Act). A person who consents is to be instructed as to the purpose for which the data to be obtained will be used.“

From relevance for genetic testing is especially section 81g on DNA analysis:

„(1) If the accused person is suspected of a criminal offence of substantial significance or of a crime against sexual self-determination then, for the purposes of establishing identity in future criminal proceedings, cell tissue may be collected from him and subjected to molecular and genetic examination for the purposes of establishing the

⁵⁴ Strafprozeßordnung in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 7. April 1987 (BGBl. I S. 1074, 1319), die zuletzt durch Artikel 2 des Gesetzes vom 30. Oktober 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3618) geändert worden ist

DNA profile or the gender if the nature of the offence or the way it was committed, the personality of the accused or other information provide grounds for assuming that criminal proceedings will be conducted against him in future in respect of a criminal offence of substantial significance. If the person concerned habitually commits other criminal offences, this may be deemed to be equivalent to a criminal offence of substantial significance by reference to the level of the injustice done.

(2) The cell tissue collected may be used only for the molecular and genetic examination referred to in subsection (1); it shall be destroyed without delay once it is no longer required for that purpose. Information other than that required in order to establish the DNA profile or the gender may not be ascertained during the examination; tests to establish such information shall be inadmissible.

(3) Without the written consent of the person concerned, the collection of cell tissue may be ordered only by the court and, in exigent circumstances, by the public prosecution office including the officials assisting it (section 152 of the Courts Constitution Act). Without the written consent of the person concerned, the molecular and genetic examination of cell tissue may be ordered only by the court. Persons who have consented are to be instructed as to the purpose for which the data to be obtained will be used. Section 81f subsection (2) shall apply mutatis mutandis. In its written reasons the court shall specify in relation to the particular case concerned

1. the determining facts relevant to ascertaining the seriousness of the criminal offence,
2. the information giving rise to the assumption that the accused will be the subject of criminal proceedings in the future, as well as
3. an evaluation of the relevant circumstances in each case.

(4) Subsections (1) to (3) shall apply mutatis mutandis if the person concerned has been convicted of the offence with binding effect or was not convicted merely on the grounds that

1. lack of criminal responsibility has been proven or cannot be ruled out,
2. he is unfit to stand trial on the grounds of insanity, or
3. lack of criminal responsibility has been proven or cannot be ruled out (section 3 of the Youth Courts Act) and the corresponding entry in the Federal Central Criminal Register or the Youth Register has not yet expired or been deleted.

(5) The data collected may be stored at the Federal Criminal Police Office and used in accordance with the Federal Criminal Police Office Act. The same shall apply

1. subject to the conditions listed in subsection (1), to the data obtained pursuant to Section 81e subsection (1), in respect of an accused person, as well as
2. to the data obtained pursuant to Section 81e subsection (2).

The data may be transmitted only for the purposes of criminal proceedings, for threat prevention and for international mutual legal assistance in respect thereof. In the case of number 1 of the second sentence, the accused is to be informed without delay that the data has been stored, and is to be instructed that he may apply for a court decision.”

Section 81h [Serial Molecular and Genetic Examination]

“(1) Where certain facts give rise to the suspicion that a felony against life, physical integrity, personal freedom or sexual self-determination has been committed, then with their written consent, persons who manifest certain significant features which may be assumed to apply to the perpetrator

1. may have cell tissue collected from them which will be
2. subjected to a molecular and genetic examination to establish gender and the DNA profile, and
3. the DNA profiles established automatically matched against the DNA profiles of trace materials, insofar as this is necessary in order to ascertain whether the trace material(s) originated from such persons and the measure is not disproportionate to the gravity of the offence, particularly in view of the number of persons affected by the measure.

(2) Any measure pursuant to subsection (1) shall require a court order. This order shall be issued in writing. The order shall designate the persons concerned by reference to specified significant features and shall give reasons. A prior examination of the persons concerned shall not be required. The decision ordering the measure shall not be contestable.

(3) Sections 81f subsection (2) and Section 81g subsection (2) shall apply mutatis mutandis to the implementation of the measure. Insofar as the data relating to the DNA profiles established by the measure is no longer necessary for clearing up the felony it shall be deleted without delay. The fact of the deletion shall be documented.

(4) The persons concerned are to be instructed in writing that the measure may only be implemented with their consent. They are also to be instructed that

1. the cell tissue collected shall be used exclusively for the molecular and genetic examination pursuant to subsection (1) and shall be destroyed without delay once they are no longer required for this purpose, and
2. that the DNA profiles established shall not be stored by the Federal Criminal Police Office for the purposes of establishing identity in future criminal proceedings.”

10. Prenatal testing/screening

Prenatal testing in vitro

According to the embryo protection act (Embryonenschutzgesetz (ESchG)) prenatal testing and screening are prohibited in Germany in general. Although in 2011, members of the German Bundestag voted by a majority for a draft law according to which prenatal testing should be permitted, as far as there is high probability for serious genetic disease or in cases in which miscarriage or stillbirth are likely. This law came into force in 2011, after a long discussion.⁵⁵

Section 3a

Pre-implantation genetic diagnosis; Authority to issue ordinances

⁵⁵ The law regulating preimplantation genetic diagnosis (preimplantation genetic diagnosis law PräimpG) was added to the embryo protection law as §3a and came to force on December 8th 2011. Act for the Protection of Embryos (The Embryo Protection Act); Gesetz zum Schutz von Embryonen (Embryonenschutzgesetz – ESchG). Of 13th December 1990 (BGBl. I p. 2746), last amended by Article 1 of the Law of 21st November 2011 (BGBl. I p. 2228).

(1) Whosoever subjects the cells of an embryo to in vitro genetic screening prior to its intrauterine transfer (pre-implantation genetic diagnosis) shall be punished with up to one year's imprisonment or a fine.

(2) Where the genetic pre-disposition of the woman from whom the egg cell was collected, or that of the man producing the sperm cell, or both, suggest that their offspring will be highly

likely to have a serious genetic illness, it shall not be an offence for anyone who intends to bring about a pregnancy to subject the cells of the embryo to state-of-the-art in-vitro genetic screening for this illness prior to intrauterine transfer, if the woman from whom the egg cell was collected gives her written consent.

Nor shall it be an offence for anyone to carry out, with the written consent of the woman from whom the egg cell was collected, pre-implantation genetic diagnosis in an embryo to identify an abnormality that would be highly likely to lead to still-birth or miscarriage.

A clarification of the terms *high probability* and *serious genetic disease* is missing, which is often criticized in the legal scholarship debate. Prenatal testing is only permitted if a written consent from the potential parents can be obtained. Furthermore, predictive testing is only allowed to be implemented when the parents become well informed about the medical, psychic and social consequences of the diagnostic, and when an ethics committee examined whether the mentioned requirements are met. For the implementation of prenatal testing, only qualified physicians in licensed centres are authorised to perform preimplantation genetic diagnosis.

Prenatal testing in vivo

Prenatal genetic testing in vivo is regulated in §15 of the Gene Engineering Act (GenDG):

“(1) A genetic examination may be performed only for medical purposes and only if the examination is aimed at certain genetic characteristics of the embryo or fetus which, according to the generally accepted scientific and technical knowledge, adversely affect their health during pregnancy or after birth , or if a treatment of the embryo or fetus with a drug is provided, the effect of which is influenced by certain genetic properties and the pregnant woman has been informed in accordance with § 9 and has consented to § 8 paragraph 1. If the sex of an embryo or fetus is determined on the occasion of an examination pursuant to sentence 1 or any other prenatal examination, the pregnant woman may be informed of this with her consent at the end of the twelfth week of pregnancy.

(2) A prenatal genetic examination, which aims to detect genetic characteristics of the embryo or the fetus for a disease that breaks out after the generally recognized state of medical science and technology until the age of 18, must not be performed.

(3) Prior to a prenatal genetic examination and after the examination result has been obtained, the pregnant woman must be given genetic counselling in accordance with § 10 (2) and (3) and, in addition, referred to the counselling claim under § 2 of the Pregnancy Conflict Act; the content of the consultation must be documented.

(...)”

11. Newborn screening

The main legal document regulating new born screening in Germany is the Childrens-guideline⁵⁶. During the second to third days of life (36 to 72 hours) after birth a few drops of blood (from the vein or heel) are taken from the newborn on a paper card, which will be sent to a screening lab. Parents have to give their consent.⁵⁷ The blood sample must be destroyed after the examination, therefore a biobank is not needed. The following disorders are tested:

- inborn errors of amino acid metabolism; phenylketonuria, hyperphenylalaninemia, maple syrup urine disease
- inborn errors of organic acid metabolism; glutaric acidemia type I, isovaleric acidemia
- Inborn errors of fatty acid metabolism
- congenital hypothyroidism
- biotinidase deficiency
- classical galactosemia
- classical congenital adrenal hyperplasia

In case the test is positive for a disorder parents will be informed immediately.

12. Advertising of genetic testing or screening

Advertising of genetic lifestyle tests or screenings is not regulated in Germany and therefore permitted. Although according to §7 Genetic Engineering Act genetic testing for medical purposes may only be carried out by a physician ("Arztvorbehalt").

Part IV Discussion and conclusion

13. Discussion and conclusion

Our analysis showed that the most relevant applicable German laws for the field of genetics and genomics are

- the **Embryo Protection Act** (Embryonenschutzgesetz – EschG) for gene editing and prenatal testing in vitro,
- the **Genetic Engineering Act** (Gendiagnostikgesetz – GenDG) for genetic testing and screening in general and for prenatal testing in vivo,
- the **Code of Criminal Procedure** (Strafprozeßordnung – StPO) for genetic testing in criminal investigations,
- the **Stem Cell Act** (Stammzellgesetz – StZG) for basic research with regard to gene editing,
- the **Basic Law** (Grundgesetz – GG) applicable for all relevant fields and

⁵⁶ An overview of the legal situation on newborn screening in Germany gives the German society on new born screening on its website: German Society on Newborn Screening. <http://www.screening-dgns.de/richtlinien.php>

⁵⁷ These are the information for parents: https://www.g-ba.de/downloads/17-98-2235/2018-02-27_Elterninformation_Erweitertes-Neugeborenen-Screening_bf.pdf

- the **Childrens-Guideline** with regard to newborn screening.

Human germline gene editing is prohibited very strictly under the Embryo Protection Act – not only the preclinical research, also basic research in this field is mostly forbidden and punished by imprisonment or a fine. Genetic testing, regulated in the Genetic Engineering Act, in the Code of Criminal Procedure and in the Embryo Protection Act, is allowed only under strict requirements. Rules for genetic testing in general concern e.g. the informed consent procedure, the role of physicians and the right of not-knowing. Regarding genotyping testing in criminal investigations it is important that at the moment in most parts of Germany only genetic fingerprinting is allowed – Bavaria is the only exception. Prenatal genetic diagnosis in vitro is only permitted as far as there is high probability for serious genetic disease or in cases in which miscarriage or stillbirth are likely. Newborn screening is regulated in the Childrens-Guideline. All newborns are screened, the parents' consent provided. The blood samples have to be destroyed immediately after examination. Advertising of genetic testing is not yet regulated in Germany.

It is not easy to say if the applicable German law is in line with values in the society or deviated from them. Some researchers and professional organisations in this field think the German rules are too strict and hinder technological developments and innovation. The legal scholarship debate shows that many Germans are arguing for a revision of the strict Embryo Protection Act. Some people also think these strict rules are necessary and should last. The revision of the Embryo Protection Act in 2011, which makes prenatal testing in vitro possible under some circumstances was the result of a very long and heated discussion. Some people think prenatal testing in vitro should be prohibited in general, others think it should be permitted in wider sense than it is now. These people assume that the German law is contradictory, because prenatal genetic testing in vitro is only allowed under special circumstances (see above) on the one hand and on the other hand abortion is allowed in Germany until the end of week 12 of pregnancy without any reason.

Nevertheless these are some views which are observable in the public debate and it is difficult to say if a majority thinks a revision of the Embryo protection act and other applicable laws is necessary. The SIENNA citizen panels could give important information here. They will be conducted, beside Greece, Spain and Poland, also in Germany by Kantar Public in April 2019. The results of these panels could give a better insight in values and opinions on genetic and genomics developments in the society.

References

National law

- Animal Welfare Act. Tierschutzgesetz in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 18. Mai 2006 (BGBl. I S. 1206, 1313), das zuletzt durch Artikel 141 des Gesetzes vom 29. März 2017 (BGBl. I S. 626) geändert worden ist. Unauthorised English translation of an earlier version of the German Animal Welfare Act. <https://www.animallaw.info/statute/germany-cruelty-german-animal-welfare-act>.
- Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany in the revised version published in the Federal Law Gazette Part III, classification number 100-1, as last amended by Article 1 of the Act of 23 December 2014 (Federal Law Gazette I p. 2438).
- Childrens-Guideline. Kinder-Richtlinie des Gemeinsamen Bundesausschusses über die Früherkennung von Krankheiten bei Kindern (Kinder-Richtlinie) in der Fassung vom 18. Juni 2015 veröffentlicht im Bundesanzeiger AT 18.08.2016 B1 zuletzt geändert am 19. Oktober 2017 veröffentlicht im Bundesanzeiger AT 15.03.2018 B2 in Kraft getreten am 16. März 2018. http://www.screening-dgns.de/Pdf/RichtlinienGesetze/RL_Screening2018-03-16.pdf
- Embryo Protection Act. Act for the Protection of Embryos; Gesetz zum Schutz von Embryonen (Embryonenschutzgesetz – ESchG). Of 13th December 1990 (BGBl. I p. 2746), last amended by Article 1 of the Law of 21st November 2011 (BGBl. I p. 2228).
- Genetic Engineering Act. Act on the Regulation of Genetic Engineering. Gesetz zur Regelung der Gentechnik. (Gentechnikgesetz - GenTG). Unauthorized translation: <http://web.uni-frankfurt.de/si/gentech/GenTGengl10-95c.pdf>
- Polizeiaufgabengesetz (PAG) in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 14. September 1990 (GVBl. S. 397, BayRS 2012-1-1-I), das zuletzt durch § 1 des Gesetzes vom 18. Mai 2018 (GVBl. S. 301, 434) geändert worden ist.
- Stem Cell Act. Act ensuring Protection of Embryos in connection with the importation and use of human embryonic stem cells, Gesetz zur Sicherstellung des Embryonenschutzes im Zusammenhang mit Einfuhr und Verwendung menschlicher embryonaler Stammzellen Stammzellgesetz (StZG- Stem Cell Act), 14 August 2008 at <http://bundesrecht.juris.de/stzg/index.html>
- Strafprozeßordnung (StPO) in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 7. April 1987 (BGBl. I S. 1074, 1319), die zuletzt durch Artikel 2 des Gesetzes vom 30. Oktober 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3618) geändert worden ist.

EU law

- Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Biomedical Research, CETS No. 195.
- Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, CETS 164 (hereinafter “Oviedo Covention”).
- Directive 2010/63/EU of the European parliament and the council.

Literature

- Andermann A, Blancquaert I, Beauchamp S, Costea I (2011) Guiding policy decisions for genetic screening: developing a systematic and transparent approach. *Public Health Genomics* 14(1):9– 16
- Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities (2015) Human genome surgery – towards a responsible evaluation of a new technology. Available at: http://www.gentechnologiebericht.de/bilder/BBAW_Human-Genome-Surgery_PDF-A1b-1.pdf
- Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities: Vierter Gentechnologiebericht. 2018. <https://www.nomos-elibrary.de/10.5771/9783845293790/vierter-gentechnologiebericht>
- German Ethics Council. Germline intervention in the human embryo: German Ethics Council calls for global political debate and international regulation. 2017. <https://www.ethikrat.org/fileadmin/Publikationen/Ad-hoc-Empfehlungen/englisch/recommendation-germline-intervention-in-the-human-embryo.pdf>
- German Reference Centre for Ethics in Lifesciences. In Focus: Predictive genetic testing. 2017. http://www.drze.de/in-focus/predictive-genetic-testing?set_language=en
- German Reference Centre for Ethics in Lifesciences. In Focus: Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis. 2015. http://www.drze.de/in-focus/preimplantation-genetic-diagnosis?set_language=en
- German research Foundation. Webpage: <http://www.dfg.de/>
- German society on new born screening. Website: German Society on Newborn Screening. <http://www.screening-dgns.de/richtlinien.php>
- Juris. Website: <https://www.juris.de/jportal/index.jsp>
- Kunig P, Völkerrecht und staatliches Recht', in: Vitzthum W. (ed), *Völkerrecht* (2nd ed, 2001).
- Leopoldina, DFG et al. The opportunities and limits of genome editing, 2015. https://www.leopoldina.org/uploads/tx_leopublication/2015_3Akad_Stellungnahme_Genome_Editing.pdf,
- Leopoldina, Statement. Predictive Genetic Diagnostics as an Instrument of Disease Prevention. 2010. https://www.leopoldina.org/uploads/tx_leopublication/201011_natEmpf_praedikative-EN_01.pdf P. VI-VII.
- Leopoldina. Website: http://www.leopoldina.org/uploads/tx_leopublication/201011_natEmpf_praedikative-DE.pdf
- Lovric D., A Constitution Friendly to International Law: Germany and its Völkerrechtsfreundlichkeit *AUYrBkIntLaw* 4; (2006) 25 *Australian Year Book of International Law* 75 of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes
- Website of the „Gentechnologiebericht“ group: <http://www.bbaw.de/en/research/gentechnologiebericht>
- Wilson JMG, Jungner G (1968) Principles and practice for screening for disease. – Geneva: World Health Organisation. *Public Health Papers* (No. 34). http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/37650/1/WHO_PHP_34.pdf.
- Zöllner M.A., Thörnich D., Rechtliche Möglichkeiten und Grenzen der Ausweitung von DNA-Analysen im Strafverfahren, in: *Zeitschrift für Internationale Strafrechtsdogmatik*, 2017, pp. 331-340.